

Reversible Medical Image Watermarking For Tamper Detection And Recovery With Run Length Encoding Compression

Siau-Chuin Liew, Siau-Way Liew and Jasni Mohd Zain

Abstract—Digital watermarking in medical images can ensure the authenticity and integrity of the image. This design paper reviews some existing watermarking schemes and proposes a reversible tamper detection and recovery watermarking scheme. Watermark data from ROI (Region Of Interest) are stored in RONI (Region Of Non Interest). The embedded watermark allows tampering detection and tampered image recovery. The watermark is also reversible and data compression technique was used to allow higher embedding capacity.

Keywords— data compression, medical image, reversible, tamper detection and recovery, watermark.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN modern health care facilities, systems such as HIS (Hospital Information System) and PACS (Picture Archiving and Communications System) form the information technology infrastructure for a hospital. Advancements in medical information system is changing the way patient records are stored, accessed and distributed. The integrity of the records such as medical images needs to be protected from unauthorized modification or destruction of information on the medical images. Current security measures used to protect the integrity of the patient records are such as VPN (Virtual Private Network), data encryption and data embedding [1].

Data encryption is being used on the Internet to protect sensitive data during transmission. It is also being used to protect medical images in the form of digital signature. The problem with digital signature is that it needs to be transmitted together with the image in a separate file or in the image header. There is also a risk of losing the signature during transmission. The signature will also be lost if the image file is converted to another format that does not allow headers. Data embedding is where related information such as digital signature can be inserted into the medical images as a watermark. Currently, there is no standard of implementation for digital watermarking. Watermark provides three objectives

in medical images [2]:

- data hiding, for embedding information to make the image useful or easier to use;
- integrity control, to verify that the image has not been modified without authorization;
- authenticity, that is to verify that the image is really what the user supposes it is.

In practice diagnoses has been performed on medical images before being directed to the long-term storage, thus the significant part of the image is already been determined by doctors involved in the diagnosing process [3]. The significant part is called ROI (Region Of Interest). Since information in medical images is not to be modified in any way, the watermark is usually being embedded in the RONI (Region Of Non Interest) as this region does not contribute in the process of diagnosis. Another option is to allow the watermark to be reversible [2]. The usage of ROI in watermarking in medical images had been used by Lim [4] and Fotopoulos [5] where ROI and RONI were defined before the process of watermark embedding. Reversible watermarking is where embedded watermark is removed and the original pixel value is restored. Research by Coatrieux [6] produced a watermarking scheme where information describing the image is embedded into medical images and can be reversed later on.

The ability of to detect tampering of a watermarked image is crucial for authentication. Once tampering is detected, tampered section can be recovered. Research by Wu [7] and Jasni [9] divides medical image into blocks and each block is embedded with the authentication message and recovery information of other blocks. Tampered blocks can then be restored using this information.

Data compression can be used to increase the embedding capacity in an image. The usage of lossless data compression allows strings of bits to be compressed before embedding. The exact bits can be decompressed later on. RLE (Run-Length Encoding) is an example of a lossless data compression technique that can be applied in an image watermarking.

In this paper, a design of a reversible tamper detection and recovery for medical image is proposed. This design will be using ROI, RONI and blocks to divide the medical image. Authentication bit, parity bit and pixels average intensity will be used to detect tampering and recovery. RLE as a data compression technique will be introduced to allow higher embedding capacity.

In the next section, watermarking in medical images and

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related work is introduced. The design of the proposed scheme is described in section three. Finally, the conclusion is in section four.

II. WATERMARKING IN MEDICAL IMAGES

Before proceeding to the design of the watermarking scheme, the foundation of digital watermarking, types of domain and performance measurement methods is discussed in this section. Fundamentally, watermarking system is shown as in Fig. 1.

Fig.1 Watermark is embedded into a image using a encoder and extracted using a decoder

The encoder, E embeds the watermark, W inside original image I by using embedding function, E as shown in equation (1).

$$E(I, W) = I_w \quad (1)$$

The output from this process is I_w , the watermarked image. The decoder, D will detect or extract the watermark, W from the original image as in equation (2).

$$D(I, I_w) = W \quad (2)$$

A. Types of domain

Watermarking techniques can be classified according to how the watermark is embedded namely within the spatial domain or in transform domains.

1) Spatial domain

One of the most direct and simple technique is to embed the watermark code into the LSBs (Least Significant Bits) of the image. Since a change in LSB corresponds a change in 1 unit of image gray value, its modification is not perceivable by human eyes. This technique is not as robust as transform domain techniques and rarely survives various attacks.

2) Transform domain

Most of the transform domain techniques embed watermark information into the transform coefficients of the cover image. DCT (Discrete Cosine Transform), DWT (Discrete Wavelet Transform) and DFT (Discrete Fourier Transform) are the three popular methods in this category. These methods require a longer computation time but they are compatible with image

compression and more robust against geometric transformation such as rotation, scaling, translation and cropping.

B. Watermarking schemes

There are very few tamper detection and recovery watermarking scheme for medical image. An example is the scheme developed by Wu [7]. The scheme divides an image into blocks and each block is embedded with the authentication message and the recovery information of other blocks. The tamper detection is based on the robust watermarking combined with modulo addition. An example from the work uses a 1024 x 1024 pixels image and divides it into 16 blocks with the size of 256x256 pixels. Hash value is calculated for each block and JPEG bits from another block is retrieve before being embedded as watermark into another block. The detection of the tampering is done by comparing the hash value embedded together with the watermark and the hash value extracted from the image. If tampering is detected, recovery information is extracted from the corresponding block. The schemes can recover the whole image or only the ROI.

Reversible watermarking had been proposed by Coatrieux [6]. Knowledge digest that gives a synthetic medical description of the medical image content is used for retrieving similar images with either same findings or different diagnoses. The knowledge digest is embedded as a reversible watermarking.

Jasni [8] developed a reversible watermarking where hash function is used to protect the ROI. Hash value of the whole image is embedded in the RONI as the watermark. The beauty of ultrasound images and all other medical images is that the LSBs for all pixels in the RONI are zeroes [8]. The watermark is reversed by simply setting the LSBs of RONI back to zero.

C. RLE

RLE is a simple lossless data compression algorithm. The exact original data can be reconstructed from the compressed data. It replaces the sequences of the same data values, an example within an image, by a count number and a single value. In a more detailed example, binary data that contains 1111100000111111 will be encoded as (6,1), (5,0) and (6,1). This will be interpreted as six 1's, five 0's and six 1's. The decimal number will then be converted to binary data that reads as (110,1), (101,0) and (110,1). As a comparison, the original binary data has 17 bits and the compressed binary data has only 12 bits. The RLE can be applied in image watermarking to achieve higher embedding capacity.

Research by Chang [10] uses RLE to encode string of a binary bitmap image in a steganographic algorithm. A pair of two bit values referred as run count and run value is used and embedded into a two-pixel block in a cover image. This algorithm is enhanced further by Lin [11] to achieve higher embedding capacity by using an additional bit to represent the encoding.

III. DESIGN

The design of this watermarking scheme is based on the scheme proposed in [9] in terms of watermark embedding, tamper detection and recovery. Further developments were made in image preparation, embedding and storing of original bits to allow this watermarking scheme to be reversible. RLE as a data compression technique is used to achieve higher embedding capacity.

A. Image preparation

Image preparation is the key for this scheme to be reversible. A different approach is taken by dividing a 640x480 pixels ultrasound image into ROI and RONI as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 Ultrasound image divided into ROI and RONI

Scheme developed by Fotopoulos [5] and Jasni [8] uses a rectangle to define the ROI of the medical image. In our scheme, four rectangles is used to form a pyramid shape for the ROI. This method allow the ROI to be more accurately defined due to the characteristic of the ultrasound image and results in more space being used for defining the RONI. There are six rectangles in the RONI. The ROI will be divided into blocks of 8x8 pixels and RONI into blocks 6x6 pixels. The number of blocks in the ROI must not exceed the number of blocks in the RONI to ensure that the original LSBs that will be removed from the ROI for watermark embedding can be stored in the RONI without storage issue.

One-to-one mapping which is similar mapping sequence proposed by [9] will be used as shown in (5) below:

$$\bar{B} = [(k \times B \bmod N_b) + 1] \quad (5)$$

where $B, \bar{B}, k \in [1, N_b]$, k is a prime number, and N_b is the total number of blocks in the ROI.

In this scheme, a unique integer $B \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, N_b\}$ is assigned to each block in the ROI. Number of blocks in the RONI is equal to the total number of blocks in the ROI. The maximum prime number $k \in [1, N_b]$ is picked. Equation (5) is applied to each block number B where \bar{B} , the number of its mapping blocks in obtained. All pairs of B and \bar{B} will form the block mapping sequence for ROI. Blocks in the RONI are also assigned with a unique integer. Each block in RONI

corresponds with the blocks in ROI. In our scheme, for example as shown in Fig.3, block x_1 is mapped to block y_1 in ROI by using equation (5). Block x_1 in the ROI with unique integer "5" for example, is mapped with block x_2 in the RONI with the same integer. The same algorithm is applied in mapping block y_1 and block y_2 .

Fig.3 Mapping sequence between blocks in ROI and RONI

B. Embedding

1) Watermark

The watermark embedding algorithm is based on the work in [9] where each block of 8x8 pixels in the ROI is divided into four sub-blocks of 4x4 pixels. The watermark in each sub-block is a block of 3x3 pixels where it contains two-bit authentication watermark and a seven-bit recovery watermark for the corresponding sub-block within block x_1 mapped to block y_1 .

A different approach is taken in the removal of LSBs significant bits. Only the LSBs for pixels which will be used for watermarking will be removed as compare to removal of LSBs for each pixel within the block as proposed by [9]. Figure 4 shows that only the block of 3x3 pixels in each sub-block where the LSBs will be set to zero. This will minimize processing time needed and ensure storage availability in the RONI for the LSBs which were removed from the ROI.

Average intensity for each block and its sub-blocks will be computed. Authentication bit and parity bit is generated for each sub-block. From the mapping sequence generated in the image preparation step, block y_1 recovery information will be stored in block x_1 . The average intensity of sub-blocks y_1 s within block y_1 , denoted as avg_y_1 s will be computed as the recovery intensity. The authentication bit, parity bit and the recovery intensity form the watermark where they will be embedded in the corresponding LSBs in the sub-blocks of x_1 .

2) Removed LSBs

It is proposed that the LSBs that were removed from the watermark embedding process to be stored in the RONI for the usage of restoring of the ROI to its original bits later. By using the example in Fig 3. and Fig 4., LSBs of block x_1 that were removed will be stored in LSBs of block x_2 in the RONI. Each of the 3x3 pixel block in the RONI will store the LSBs that were removed from the corresponding sub-block in the ROI by matching the block number that were assigned in the preparation step.

Fig.4 Block x1 and block x2

C. Tamper detection and recovery

The ROI of the image is divided blocks of 8x8 pixels and the LSBs in the sub-block of 4x4 pixels will be removed, as in the watermarking embedding process.

As proposed by Jasni [9], the average intensity of the block will be computed. For each sub-block of 4x4 pixels, authentication bit and parity bit will be extracted. The LSBs in the sub-block will be set to zero and average intensity for each sub-block will be computed. Authentication bit and parity bit generated from the average intensity of block and sub-block will be compared to know whether the block is tampered. Tampered blocks will be recovered by locating its corresponding blocks by using the mapping sequence used in image preparation. By referring to Fig 3., with the assumption that block y1 had been tampered and its recovery bits were stored in block x1, the average intensity of each sub-block of block y1 stored in sub-blocks of block x1 will be obtained. Block y1 will be replaced with the recovered average intensity bits.

D. Reversible watermark

As an addition function to the scheme by Jasni [9], it is proposed that the embedded watermark can be reversed by restoring removed LSBs during the watermark embedding process. Removed LSBs of block x1 were stored in block x2 in the RONI as shown in Fig.3. The LSBs of each sub-block x1 will be replaced with its original bits that were stored in the 6x6 pixels of block x2 as shown in Fig.4. The process is applied to every block in the ROI. The LSBs of each pixel in RONI will be reset back to its original value which is zero.

E. RLE

The usage of RLE as a lossless data compression will result in a higher embedding capacity in the RONI. This allows the block size in the ROI to be divided into blocks of 4x4 pixels instead of 8x8 pixels blocks. This will increase the quality of the recovered tampered area in the ROI where recovered area is represented by 4x4 pixels blocks.

By using the example of block x1 as shown in Fig.5, a total of 36 removed LSBs from block x1 in the ROI will be compressed and stored in the LSBs of RONI. The RONI is divided into blocks of 2x2 pixels that consist of three bits to represent the number of repetition, denoted as RC and one bit

to represent the binary value, denoted as RV. Since RC has only three bits representation, the maximum value that can be represented is seven. For example, LSBs value of 11111100001111100000 will be interpreted as seven 1's, four 0's, five 1's and 5 0's. The encoded value for seven 1's will be RC=111, RV=1 and for four 0's will be RC=100, RV=0. The rest of the bits will be encoded in the same manner and to be embedded in sequence of 2x2 pixel blocks in the RONI.

Fig.5 Compression using RLE

The decoding of the embedded RLE is done by extracting the LSBs stored in the 2x2 pixels block in the RONI. All the three bits of RC and one bit RV will be retrieved to be decompressed to form the original 36 LSBs of a block in the ROI. The corresponding block will be restored using the decompressed bits. The process is repeated for the rest of the compressed bits in the RONI.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper proposed a design of a reversible tamper detection and recovery watermarking for medical images. A reversible watermarking scheme is crucial to allow the original pixel values to be restored. RLE were introduced to compress the removed LSBs from the ROI before being embedded into RONI. This will allow the ROI to be divided into smaller blocks to increase the quality of the recovered image. Further testing is required to know the perceptibility of the watermarked image. An area of possible further development is the security of the embedded original pixel value in the RONI. Hash function can be used to verify the authenticity and integrity of the original pixel values.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Cao,F.,Huang,H.K.,Zhou,X.Q., "Medical image security in a HIPAA mandated PACS environment",*Computerized Medical Imaging and Graphics*,2003,vol 27,pp.185-196, doi:10.1016/S0895-6111(02)00073-3
- [2] Coatrieux, G., Main, H., Sankur, B., Rolland, Y., Collorec, R., "Relevance of watermarking in medical imaging", in *Proc. of IEEE-EMBS Information Technology Applications in Biomedicine*, 2000 pp. 250-255, doi:10.1109/ITAB.2000.892396.
- [3] Wakatani,A., "Digital Watermarking for ROI Medical Images by Using Compressed Signature Image," in *Proc. 35th Annual Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS-35'02)*, 2002, pp. 2043-2048.
- [4] Lim,Sung Jin,Moon, Hae Min,Chae, Seung-Hoon,Pan, Sung Bum, Yongwha Chung, Min Hyuk Chang, "Dual watermarking method for integrity of medical images", in *Proc. of Second International Conference on Future Generation Communication and Networking*, 2008, vol.2, pp.70-73, doi: 10.1109/FGCN.2008.
- [5] Fotopoulos,V., Stavrinou ,M.L., Skodras,A.N., "Medical image authentication and self-correction through an adaptive reversible watermarking technique " in *Proc. of the 8th IEEE International Conference on Bioinformatics and BioEngineering*, Oct 2008, pp.1-5,doi: 10.1109/BIBE.2008.4696803.
- [6] Coatrieux, G, Le Guillou, C., Cauvin, J.-M., Roux, C., "Reversible watermarking for knowledge digest embedding and reliability control in medical images", *IEEE Transactions on Information Technology in Biomedicine*, vol 13, issue 2, Mac 2009,pp.158 - 165,doi: 10.1109/TITB.2008.2007199.
- [7] Wu ,Jeffery H. K, Chang ,Ruey-Feng, Chen,Chii-Jen, Wang ,Ching-Lin, Kuo ,Ta-Hsun, Moon,Woo Kyung ,Che ,Dar-Ren, "Tamper detection and recovery for medical images using near-lossless information hiding technique", *Journal of Digital Imaging*, Mac 2008 , vol 21,No 1,pp. 59-76,doi: 10.1007/s10278-007-9011-1.
- [8] Jasni M. Zain, L.P Balwin,M.Clarke,"Reversible watermarking for authentication of DICOM images", in *Proc. 26th Annual International Conference of the IEEE EMBS*,San Francisco,USA Sep 2004,pp. 3237 - 3240 ,ISBN: 0-7803-8439-3.
- [9] Jasni M. Zain, Abdul R.M. Fauzi, "Medical Image Watermarking with Tamper Detection and Recovery", in *Proc. 28th Annual International Conference of the IEEE EMBS*, New York,USA,Sept. 2006,pp. 3270-3273,doi: 10.1109/IEMBS.2006.260767.
- [10] Chang, Chin-Chen, Lin, Chih-Yang, Wang, Yu-Zheng , "New image steganographic methods using run-length approach", *Information Sciences*, Volume 176, Issue 22, 22 November 2006, Pages 3393-3408, ISSN 0020-0255, doi: 10.1016/j.ins.2006.02.008.
- [11] Lin ,Rey-Sern, Hu,Shang-Wen, "A Modified Run-length Image Data Hiding for High Embedding Capacity," *Information Assurance and Security, International Symposium on, Fifth International Conference on Information Assurance and Security*,2009, pp. 673-676, doi: 10.1109/IAS.2009.35.